

Synthesis and crystal structure of bis(2-aminopyridinium) tetrachlorocuprate(II)

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The synthesis and crystal structure of orange 2-aminopyridinium tetrachlorocuprate(II), $(C_5H_7N_2)_2CuCl_4$, have been reported. The compound crystallizes in $P\bar{1}$ space group and contains discrete tetrahedral $CuCl_4^{2-}$ species and 2-aminopyridinium cations. An extensive molecular association through the hydrogen bonding involving all the chlorine atoms is also observed in the crystallizing environment of the title compound.

The extremely diverse and interesting crystal chemistry of Cu^{II} results from the presence of active Jahn-Teller effect in the d^9 electronic system and the relative flatness of potential surfaces¹. For $CuCl_4^{2-}$ species, the coordination geometries range from nearly tetrahedral with a D_{2d} distortion, to a completely planar D_{4h} species^{2,3}. The counter cation, to be more precise the effectiveness of hydrogen bonding involving the protonated cationic part and the chloride ion of the discrete anionic $CuCl_4^{2-}$ species, i.e. N-H...Cl hydrogen bond has an important role in the geometry of $CuCl_4^{2-}$. In general, the stronger the hydrogen bonding, the closer the anions are to a square planar coordination. The geometry as well as the colour of such compounds can successfully be described by the average *trans* angle value. It exhibits yellow-green colour at RT when the *trans* angle is 140° ⁵. The colour changes to deeper green as the angle increases and towards orange as the angle decreases^{6,7}. In some cases, the hydrogen bonding network is temperature dependant causing thermochromism of such species. In continuation of our study to have structural insight of chlorocuprates with organic cations, we report here the synthesis and structural investigations of bis(2-aminopyridinium) tetrachlorocuprate, $(C_5H_7N_2)_2CuCl_4$.

Results and discussion

The crystal structure of bis(2-aminopyridinium) tetrachlorocuprate(II) consists of a discrete tetrahedral tetrachlorocuprate anion and two 2-aminopyridinium cations. Fig. 1 represents an ORTEP view of the compound with the atom numbering scheme. The $CuCl_4^{2-}$ anion assumes a distorted tetrahedral geometry which is consistent

Fig. 1. ORTEP drawing of the complex showing the atom numbering scheme.

with the anticipated distortions predicted by Jahn-Teller effect¹⁻³. These distortions are typically measured by the value of the *trans* Cl-Cu-Cl angle, which are 180° for square planar and 109.5° for tetrahedral structures. The two angles are $130.18^\circ(3)$ and $136.43^\circ(3)$ in the present compound⁴. The considerable spread (6°) between the two independent angles is due to the constraints imposed by the hydrogen bonding in the structure. Such spread has also been found in some related systems⁸. The observed orange colour of compound **1** is also consistent with the average value of the *trans* angle (133.31°). Three dimensional stability is given to the structure by hydrogen bonding between the 2-aminopyridinium cations and chloride ions as well as the stacking of the organic cations. The two 2-aminopyridinium rings in the molecule are almost planar with deviations rang-

ing between $-0.005(3)$ to $0.006(3)$ Å and the dihedral angle between them is 74° . Protonation of the 2-amino-pyridine molecule occurs at the ring nitrogen atom and the geometry at the amine nitrogen is planar indicating significant π delocalisation between the pyridine ring and the amine nitrogen. This is substantiated by the short amine nitrogen-ring carbon bond distances (1.32 Å avg.) which are very close to the ring carbon-nitrogen distances (1.35 Å avg.). Here, the amine hydrogen atoms, H1a and H1b, attached to the nitrogen atom, N1, and the hydrogen atoms, H4a and H4b, attached to another nitrogen atom, N4, forms extensive hydrogen bonding network. Again, the ring hydrogen atoms, H1 and H3a, attached to the nitrogen atoms N2 and N3 respectively also have important contribution to structural association through the hydrogen bonding. It is interesting to note that the Cl atoms, Cl1 and Cl4, are acting as the acceptors of two hydrogen bonds, whereas the other two Cl atoms, Cl2 and Cl3, are the acceptors of single hydrogen bonds. Another interesting feature of the structure is that one Cu–Cl (Cl4) distance is about 0.03 Å longer than the other three which are nearly equal. In the chlorocuprates, it has been found that the longer Cu–Cl distances are associated with the chlorine atoms which are engaged in more extensive or stronger hydrogen bonding. Here, both Cl1 and Cl4 are acceptors of two hydrogen bonds with almost equal N...Cl distances. But the average H...Cl distance associated with Cl4 (2.46 Å) is less than that of Cl1 (2.52 Å) and the average N–H...Cl angle (173.93°) with Cl4 is larger than that of Cl1 (153.78°) which indicates that the more effective hydrogen bonding is associated with Cl4. A PLUTO packing diagram showing the stacking of the molecules in an extended environment is shown in Fig. 2. It is found that the 2-aminopyridine ring containing N2, C1, N1, C2, C3, C4, and C5 which is almost perpendicular to the *ab* plane stacks antiparallely in the same direction at 2.931 Å interval while the other 2-aminopyridinium moiety containing N4, C6, N3, C10, C9, C8 and C7 which forms a 74° angle with the former also stacks antiparallely at 3.521 Å. The shortest C–H...Cl distance is more than 3.816 Å, which excludes an C–H...Cl interactions.

IR and electronic spectra :

The FT-IR spectrum of the compound exhibits four absorption bands above 3000 cm^{-1} (3362 , 3312 , 3180 and 3081 cm^{-1}) arise from the N–H stretching vibrations. The presence of four bands may be attributed to an unequal involvement of the hydrogen atoms of the amino groups and ring nitrogens in hydrogen bonding. The spectra also show a strong peak at 1661 cm^{-1} due to $\delta(\text{C–N})$. The appearance of the peak at such a high frequency substantiate the ob-

Fig. 2. Crystal packing arrangement showing hydrogen bonding scheme and the stacking of 2-aminopyridinium moieties. The dotted lines indicate hydrogen bonds.

Table 1. Crystal data and structure refinement details

Empirical formula	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{Cl}_4\text{CuN}_4$	
Formula weight	393.58	
Crystal system, space group	Triclinic, $P\bar{1}$	
Unit cell dimensions	$a = 7.981(2)$ Å	$\alpha = 91.248(4)^\circ$
	$b = 8.137(2)$ Å	$\beta = 94.763(3)^\circ$
	$c = 13.645(3)$ Å	$\gamma = 114.935(3)^\circ$
Volume	$799.2(3)$ Å ³	
Z, Calculated density	2, 1.636 mg/m ³	
Absorption coefficient	2.025 mm^{-1}	
$F(000)$	394	
Crystal colour	Orange	
θ range for data collection	2.77 to 27.58°	
Limiting indices	$-7 \leq h \leq 10$	
	$-10 \leq k \leq 6$	
	$17 \leq l \leq 17$	
Reflections measured	5165	
R (int)	0.0226	
Completeness to $\theta = 28.09^\circ$	92.2%	
Refinement method	Full-matrix least-squares on F^2	
Data/restraints/parameters	3563/0/172	
Crystal dimensions	$0.26 \times 0.19 \times 0.14$ mm	
Goodness-of-fit on F^2	0.948	
Final R indices [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	$R1 = 0.0315$, $wR2 = 0.0949$	
R indices (all data)	$R1 = 0.0400$, $wR2 = 0.0986$	
Extinction coefficient	$0.0003(2)$	
Largest diff. peak and hole	0.611 and -0.451 eÅ^3	

Table 2. Bond lengths (Å) and angles (°) with e.s.d. 's in parentheses.

Cu1–Cl2	2.2322(3)
Cu1–Cl3	2.2389(4)
Cu1–Cl1	2.2361(3)
Cu1–Cl4	2.2681(3)
N2–C1	1.3431(2)
N2–C5	1.3634(2)
C1–N1	1.3263(2)
C1–C2	1.4017(2)
C5–C4	1.3343(2)
C2–C3	1.3576(2)
C3–C4	1.3969(3)
N3–C6	1.3366(2)
N3–C10	1.3612(2)
C6–N4	1.3311(2)
C6–C7	1.4072(2)
C8–C9	1.3918(2)
C8–C7	1.3528(2)
C9–C10	1.3422(2)
Cl(2)–Cu(1)–Cl(1)	98.80(3)
Cl(2)–Cu(1)–Cl(3)	99.77(3)
Cl(1)–Cu(1)–Cl(3)	136.43(3)
Cl(2)–Cu(1)–Cl(4)	130.18(3)
Cl(1)–Cu(1)–Cl(4)	97.80(3)
Cl(3)–Cu(1)–Cl(4)	99.58(3)

Table 3. Hydrogen bonding distances (Å) and angles (°)

D–H ... A	D–H	D ... A	H ... A	∠D–H ... A
N(2)–H(1) ... Cl(1)	0.8601	3.2519	2.5425	140.41
N(1)–H(1a) ... Cl(4)	0.8600	3.2932	2.4446	172.27
N(1)–H(1b) ... Cl(1)	0.8601	3.3462	2.5022	167.16
N(3)–H(3a) ... Cl(3)	0.8601	3.1710	2.3351	164.08
N(4)–H(4a) ... Cl(2)	0.8601	3.2663	2.4282	164.89
N(4)–H(4b) ... Cl(4)	0.8601	3.3350	2.4770	175.59

served short C–NH₂ bond distance (Table 2) in the crystal structure, attributable to the significant π delocalisation between the pyridine ring and the amine nitrogen.

The colour of the CuCl₄²⁻ species depends upon the Cl → Cu charge transfer transition which lies close to the uv-vis boundary of the spectrum. The yellow → green colour change occurs due to an increased splitting in the primarily *d* orbital levels as the anion approaches the square planar limit. This charge transfer band with a peak appears at 390 nm for the present compound in the electronic spectra of nujol mull and is consistent with its tetrahedral geometry.

Experimental

High purity (98%) benzimidazole and copper(II) chloride, dihydrate were purchased from Lancaster, England and E. Merck, India respectively and used as received. Elemental analyses (carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen) were performed using a Perkin-Elmer 240C elemental analyzer and the copper contents in the complex was estimated spectrophotometrically⁹. IR spectra in KBr (4500–500 cm⁻¹) were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer RXI FT-IR spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra of mulls (1200–350 nm) were recorded with a Hitachi U-3501 spectrophotometer where nujol was used as a medium as well as a reference. The effective magnetic moments were calculated from magnetic susceptibility measurements with an EG and G PAR vibrating sample magnetometer model 155 at RT and diamagnetic corrections were made using Pascal's constants¹⁰.

(C₅H₇N₂)₂CuCl₄: The title compound was prepared by dissolving 5 mmoles of CuCl₂·2H₂O in minimum volume of water and 4 ml of concentrated HCl, 10 mmoles of 2-aminopyridine dissolved in minimum volume of water were then added. The resulting solution was left to evaporate slowly. After a few days, orange-yellow crystals suitable for X-ray analysis were obtained. Anal. Found (calcd.): C, 30.4 (30.3); H, 3.4 (3.5); N, 14.2 (13.9); Cu, 16.4 (16.1)%; μ_{eff} 1.75 B.M. at 278 K; λ_{max} 390 nm.

Crystallography: Suitable single crystal of the complex was mounted on a Bruker AXS CCD area detector system for data collection. The crystal data of the complex were collected at 293(2) K. Intensity data were collected in the ω -2 θ scan mode using graphite monochromated Mo-K α radiation (0.71073 Å). The empirical absorption corrections were based on ψ scans. The crystal data and structure refinement parameters are given in Table 1. Cu atom present in the molecule was obtained by Patterson method using the program SHELX 86. Successive difference fourier using initially the phase contribution of the Cu atom revealed the remaining non-hydrogen atoms of the molecule SHELX 97¹¹ was used for this purpose. The coordinates of the model structure determined were then put through full matrix least squares method of refinement. The structure was first refined isotropically varying the positional parameters and isotropic thermal parameters of the non hydrogen atoms together with the overall scale factor. Further least square refinements of the coordinates of non hydrogen atoms were done using anisotropic temperature factors. The hydrogen atoms were placed geometrically and refined in the "riding" model with isotropic thermal parameters 1.2 times U_{eq} of the atom to which they were attached and were

treated as fixed contributors to the final structure factor calculations. Complex neutral atom scattering factors were used throughout the refinement. All calculations were carried out using SHELX 97¹¹, PLATON 99¹² and ORTEP¹³ programs. Selected crystallographic data for the compound are displayed in Table 1 while selected bond lengths and bond angles of the compound are presented in Table 2. Table 3 lists the significant hydrogen bonding characteristics.

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